

MAGNETIC EVIDENCE REGARDING THE VALENCY OF COLOURANT IONS IN GLASS PART II.

By N. A. YAJNIK, RAM CHAND AND D. C. JAIN

Valency and the state of iron ions in glasses prepared by using borax and microcosmic salt have been determined with the aid of chemical analysis and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Conditions of iron oxide as such corresponding to different colours in glasses have been shown.

Two papers have already been published from this laboratory regarding the nature of colourant ions in glass (Bhatnagar, *Nature*, 1939, **143**, 599; Bhatnagar, Khosla and Ram Chand, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 515) in which the authors have investigated the state of manganese, cobalt and nickel in phosphate glasses. Magnetic susceptibility measurements have been used to find out the valency and the state of colourant ions.

Iron is another element which has been used for colouring glasses and glazes and it has been claimed to impart all the colours of spectrum to them (*cf.* Bancroft and Cunningham, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 1). But it is usually employed to give yellow and green colours.

Bancroft and Cunningham (*loc. cit.*) have used different amounts of boric acid and alkalis to prepare the glasses and have concluded that iron in the reduced state gives green colour, while in the oxidised condition the colour is yellow.

In the present investigation borax as well as microcosmic salt have been used to prepare the glasses. With the aid of chemical analysis and magnetic susceptibility measurements the valency and the state of iron ions, as well as the condition of iron oxide as such corresponding to different colours, have been shown.

Magnetic susceptibility of iron ions in different states of valency has been calculated by Stoner and Van Vleck formula.

$$\chi_M = \frac{n\beta^2}{3kT} \left[4s(s+1) + l(l+1) \right]$$

where s and l are spin and orbital moments.

Guoy type balance was used to find the magnetic susceptibilities. The same technique was followed to prepare the glasses as by Bhatnager, Khosla and Ram Chand (*loc. cit.*).

In the case of borax glasses iron imparted a yellow colour in oxidising and green in reducing conditions, when cold. In the case of microcosmic glasses yellowish brown and greenish brown colours were obtained in corresponding conditions.

TABLE I

Total iron.	Fe ^{II} in total iron.	χ_{glass} $\times 10^4$	χ_M (Fe) ionic $\times 10^4$.			Total iron.	Fe ^{II} in total iron.	χ_{glass} $\times 10^4$	χ_M (Fe) ionic		
			obs.	calculated with l operative.	quenched.				obs.	calculated with l operative.	quenched.
Reduced microcosmic glasses						Oxidised microcosmic glasses					
1'772%	14'41%	4'070	251'8	260'1	253'4	1'795	3'70	4'263	260'3	264'2	262'2
2'621	17'30	6'167	250'0	259'0	251'0	1'121	7'95	2'510	258'7	262'4	258'8
2'183	13'08	5'250	253'1	260'6	254'5	2'100	2'10	5'062	259'4	264'7	263'4
1'950	15'00	4'528	252'0	259'8	253'0	3'010	2'90	7'464	260'6	264'3	263'0
Oxidised borax glasses						Reduced borax glasses					
1'189	...	2'704	262'4	—	—	1'039	33'02	2'030	240'1	253'0	237'9
1'024	—	2'317	266'9	—	—	1'189	55'50	2'200	220'0	244'2	218'7

Total iron was estimated by reduction to ferrous state with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid and titration with dichromate solution. Ferrous content of glasses was estimated by dissolving a known weight of the glass in a known volume of standard permanganate solution in cold, and back-titrating with standard ferrous sulphate solution.

In the case of ferrous state l moment can be operative as well as quenched. Therefore χ_m (ionic) has been calculated for both these conditions and the results tabulated along with the results obtained from actual experimental data.

Magnetic susceptibilities (observed and calculated) and results of analyses of various types of glasses are given in Table I.

TABLE II

Susceptibility values obtained at different temperatures.

Temp.	—	289°	325°	359°	421°	470°
$\chi_m \times 10^6$	...	262.4	231.0	202.3	171.8	155.4
C_m	..	4.198	4.125	4.025	4.015	4.056

Mean value for $C_m = 4.084$.

$$\mu_n = 5.74.$$

Calculating the ionic susceptibilities of iron from Stoner-Van Vleck formula, χ_m (ionic) for Fe^{III} ions which are in ${}^6S_{5/2}$ state is 265.5×10^{-6} at 25° . χ_m (ionic) for Fe^{II} ions which are in 5D_4 state i.e., $l=2$ and $s=3$ is 182.0×10^{-6} at 25° where l is quenched and 227.5×10^{-6} at 25° where l is operative.

Calculating the ionic susceptibility of iron from the analytical data and comparing it with the observed values in Table I, we find that values obtained when l moment is quenched agree better with observed values than when it is operative. It has been noted by Sommerfield ("Atombau" 4th Ed. p. 631), Bose (*Z. Physik*, 1927, 43, 864), and Stoner (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, 8, 250) that in the case of ions of the iron group l moment is fully quenched.

A borax glass prepared in the oxidising atmosphere was tried at various temperatures to get the value of Bohr magneton for ferric ions. Results are tabulated in Table I. Curie point has been determined by plotting $1/\chi$ and T and reading the intercept on T axis. $\theta = 2.3$ and $\mu_n = 5.74$ which agrees fairly well with the theoretical value 5.9 for trivalent iron where l is quenched.

